

COMPARISON OF MICROMECHANICS THEORIES FOR MODELING CHOPPED CARBON FIBER POLYMER MATRIX COMPOSITES

Evan J. Pineda^{1*}, Ibrahim Kaleel², Brett A. Bednarcyk¹ and Sandi G. Miller³

¹ Multiscale and Multiphysics Modeling Branch, NASA Glenn Research Center, Cleveland, U.S.A.,

² NASA Postdoctoral Program, Oak Ridge Associated Universities, Cleveland, U.S.A.,

³ Ceramic and Polymer Composites Branch, NASA Glenn Research Center, Cleveland, U.S.A.

*Corresponding author (evan.j.pineda@nasa.gov)

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Outline

- Overview of Tailored Universal Feedstock for Forming (TuFF)
- Objective
- Micromechanics
 - High fidelity generalized method of cells (HFGMC)
 - Carrera Unified Formulation (CUF)
- Simple single fiber Repeating Unit Cell (RUC) model
- Results
- Conclusion/Future Work

Tailored Universal Feedstock for Forming (TuFF)

Yarlagadda, et al. (2019), SAMPE, Charlotte, NC;

Discrete Long Fibers (Len./Dia ≥ 600)

In-plane properties similar to continuous fiber composites

Sample	Fiber	Length (mm)	Resin	E_{11} (GPa)	CV (%)	χ_T (MPa)	CV (%)	ϵ_{11}	FVF
IM7/8552	IM7	Cont	8552	162	2.27	2558	4.1	1.58%	57.30%
180507_1xA_6:1	IM7	3	PEI	143	1.61	2255	2.01	1.51%	52%
180620_1xA_8:1	IM7	3	PEI	168	1.46	2503	3.19	1.42%	61%
180620_1xB_9:1	IM7	3	PEI	173	1.71	2668	2.96	1.49%	63%
180724_1xC_7:1	IM7	3	PEI	161	1.36	2579	3.67	1.51%	58%
180724_1xB_8:1	IM7	3	PEI	168	1.78	2551	5.86	1.48%	61%
Commercial (Cytec)	AS4	Cont	PEI	134	1.3	2406	4.8	1.64%	55.5%
Cytec AS4/PEI 2-ply	AS4	Cont	PEI	137	5.46	2289	7.82	1.54%	55.5%

Highly Aligned

Formability

Enabling Technology!

- Rapid and advanced manufacturing
 - Stretch forming, stamping, tow steering, AFP
- Complex parts
- Recyclability (thermoplastic matrix)

Why Model TuFF?

- Composite behavior highly dependent on microstructure
- Virtual manufacturing, testing and progressive damage and failure analysis (PDFA)
 - Rapid product development
 - Improved material design
 - Improved material performance
- Micromechanics and multiscale modeling is a useful tool
 - Can relate microstructure to properties
 - Can understand the local physics that drive the global phenomena

Objective

- Evaluate micromechanics theories
 - Potential for modeling multi-fiber representative volume elements (RVE)
 - Nonlinear modeling – PDFFA, process modeling
 - Accuracy – must be able to capture shear lag effect
 - Efficiency – RVE simulations will be large
- Preliminary work – study single fiber repeating unit cell (RUC)
- Two micromechanics theories considered here
 - HFGMC – faster than traditional FEA
 - Amenable to multiscale modeling
 - CUF – based on arbitrary order beam theory
 - Suitable for modeling discrete fibers explicitly

HFGMC – Theory Overview

- Microstructure idealized with a discretized repeating unit cell (RUC)
 - Microstructure and material behavior are arbitrary

- Subcell displacements are assumed quadratic

$$u_i^{(\alpha\beta\gamma)} = \bar{\varepsilon}_{ij} x_j + W_{i(000)}^{(\alpha\beta\gamma)} + \bar{y}_1^{(\alpha)} W_{i(100)}^{(\alpha\beta\gamma)} + \bar{y}_2^{(\beta)} W_{i(010)}^{(\alpha\beta\gamma)} + \bar{y}_3^{(\gamma)} W_{i(001)}^{(\alpha\beta\gamma)} \\ + \frac{1}{2} \left(3\bar{y}_1^{(\alpha)2} - \frac{d_\alpha^2}{4} \right) W_{i(200)}^{(\alpha\beta\gamma)} + \frac{1}{2} \left(3\bar{y}_2^{(\beta)2} - \frac{h_\beta^2}{4} \right) W_{i(020)}^{(\alpha\beta\gamma)} + \frac{1}{2} \left(3\bar{y}_3^{(\gamma)2} - \frac{l_\gamma^2}{4} \right) W_{i(002)}^{(\alpha\beta\gamma)}$$

- Efficient semi-analytical solution

- Continuity of traction and displacements
 - Enforced in an integral sense at subcell interfaces

- Strain concentration matrix maps global strains to local strains

- Piecewise linear, 3D local stresses and strains

CUF – Theory Overview

- Arbitrary choice for the type and order (number of terms) of the expansion

CUF Kinematic field: $u(x, y, z) = F_\tau(x, z) u(y)$

- Formulated as an invariant through Fundamental nuclei - same implementation for different classes of models
- Formulated within the context of finite element using standard shape function:

CUF beam element

Kinematic field:

$$u_x(x, y, z) = u_{x1} + u_{x2}x + u_{x3}z + \dots$$

$$u_y(x, y, z) = u_{y1} + u_{y2}x + u_{y3}z + \dots$$

$$u_z(x, y, z) = u_{z1} + u_{z2}x + u_{z3}z + \dots$$

$$F_\tau = \frac{1}{2}(r^2 + rr_\tau)(s^2 + ss_\tau) \quad \tau = 1, 3, 5, 7$$

$$F_\tau = \frac{1}{2}r_\tau^2(r^2 + rr_\tau)(1 - s^2) + \frac{1}{2}s_\tau^2(s^2 + ss_\tau)(1 - r^2) \quad \tau = 2, 4, 6, 8$$

$$F_\tau = (1 - r^2)(1 - s^2) \quad \tau = 9$$

RUC Model Details

Aspect Ratio (L_f/D_f)	600
Gap Ratio (D_g/L_f)	0.005 – 0.05
Fiber Volume Fraction (F_f)	0.58

Axial Discretization

Cross Section Discretization

HFGMC

CUF

- Periodic boundary conditions
- Uniaxial strain ϵ_x applied in the longitudinal direction

Runtimes (Single CPU on a Laptop)

HFGMC	CUF
~ 12 mins	~ 6 mins

Stiffness as a Function of Gap Ratio

 E_{xx}

 E_{yy}

Poisson's Ratio as a Function of Gap Ratio

Shear Stiffness as a Function of Gap Ratio

 G_{xy}

 G_{yz}

Average Stress in Fiber and Matrix

Gap Ratio $D_g/L_f = 0.005$

Gap Ratio $D_g/L_f = 0.005$

● HFGMC - Fiber
 ● HFGMC - Matrix
 ● CUF - Fiber
 ● CUF - Matrix

Axial Stress Along Centerline

Shear Stress Along Centerline

Conclusion

- Single fiber RUC for a discrete long fiber composite modeled with HFGMC and CUF
 - Length to diameter aspect ratio = 600
- Axial stiffness sensitive to gap size
- Calculation of average stress in fiber and matrix match well between models
 - Local stress fields are complex
 - Large gradients and stress spikes
 - Discrepancy between models in shear stress along centerline

Future Work

- Understand reason for discrepancy in shear stresses
- Develop strategy for modeling multiple fibers
 - Computational requirements will pose a problem
- Incorporate damage model
- Incorporate rate dependent constitutive model to capture stretch forming at high temperatures
- Integrate multiscale model for semi-crystalline thermoplastic

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Questions/Comments/Suggestions?